

Problems Faced by Street Children in India

R.Dhanalakshmi & M.Durgadevi

M.Ed. Scholar, 1 Year

J.J.College of Education, Pudukkottai

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2653

Impact Factor: 4.012

Citation:

Dhanalakshmi, R., and M. Durgadevi. “Problems Faced by Street Children in India.” *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 93–96.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2599856>

Abstract

Street children are the most unprotected group in any society and their problem is a global one and exists in both, the developed as well as developing countries though differing in size and magnitude. Street and working children are a universal sight in industrial and civilized cities and they have been accepted as a necessary evil and the product of urban poverty, overpopulation and breakdown of family system and are labeled as Children in difficult circumstances by UNICEF. Issue of street children has become a serious social problem. If proper steps are not taken, one-day social stability will be at stake. Thus, the paper highlights an overview of street children in India. Street children are deprived of minimal basic facilities in life.

Introduction

India has an estimated one hundred thousand or more street children in each of the following cities: New Delhi, Kolkata, and Mumbai. Mainly because of family conflict, they come to live on the streets and take on the full responsibilities of caring for themselves, including working to provide for and protecting themselves. Though street children do sometimes band together for greater security, they are often exploited by employers and the police.

Their much vulnerability requires specific legislation and attention from the government and other organizations to improve their condition.

There are believed to be about 11 million street children in India. No two children’s stories are identical, but there are some clear common factors at the root of : poverty, hunger and abuse.

Reason Behind children’s Lives in Streets

India has made massive strides in fighting poverty over the last couple of decades, reducing the rate to about 20%. But huge problems remain, made worse by rapid population growth. Despite major development in some of northern India’s poorer states, thousands of villages continue to lack the facilities that are available in cities.

Tens of millions of children remain out of school, or are enrolled but in places without adequate teachers or facilities. All these factors help push a constant stream of children towards the big cities. Others are pulled by the lure of employment, friends or perhaps the distant dream of Bollywood stardom.

UNICEF

UNICEF is defined as United Nations Children’s Fund, formerly (1946–53) United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund, special program of the United Nations (UN) devoted to aiding national efforts to improve the health, nutrition, education, and general welfare of children. According to UNICEF street children fall under two categories:

- Children of the street
- Children on the street

“Children of the street” are homeless children who live and sleep on the streets in urban areas. They are on their own and do not have any parental supervision or care though some do live with other homeless adults.

“Children on the street” earn a livelihood from streets such as street urchins and beggars. They return home at night and have contact with their families. The distinction is an important one because children of the street lack emotional and psychological support of a family. street children in India

The Problems of Street Children

- Abuse
- Child Labour
- Gender Discrimination
- Health
- Homelessness
- Poverty

Abuse

Many of the street children who have run away from home have done so because they were beaten or sexually abused. Tragically, their homelessness can lead to further abuse through exploitative child labor and prostitution.

Many of the abused children I-India encounters are traumatized and some refuse to speak for months. To aggravate matters, children often feel guilty and blame themselves for their mistreatment. Such damage can take years to recover from in even the most loving of environments; on the streets it may never heal.

Child Labour

Most Indian street children work. In Jaipur, a common job is rag-picking, in which boys and girls as young as 6 years old sift through garbage to collect recyclable material. The children usually rise before dawn and carry their heavy load in a large bag over their shoulder. Rag-pickers can be seen alongside pigs and dogs searching through trash heaps on their hands and knees.

Other common jobs are the collecting of firewood, tending to animals, street vending, dyeing, begging, prostitution and domestic labor.

Children that work are not only subject to the strains and hazards of their labour, but are also denied the education or training that could enable them to escape the poverty trap.

Gender Discrimination

In Indian Society females are often discriminated against. Their health, education, prosperity and freedom are all impacted. The problem is worse in conservative Rajasthan than almost anywhere else in India.

Gender discrimination is particularly evident in education where boys are more likely to attend school and to do so for more years.

The traditional place of the woman is in the home and so many parents and children consider education for girls to be a waste of time, especially when the child can instead be working or performing domestic chores..

Child Marriage is another way in which girls are disadvantaged. In addition to limiting educational possibilities and stunting personal development, early marriage carries health risks. A girl under 15 is five times more likely to die during pregnancy than women in her twenties; her child is also more likely to die.

Health

Poor health is a chronic problem for street children. Half of all children in India are malnourished, but for street children the proportion is much higher. These children are not only underweight, but their growth has often been stunted;

for example, it is very common to mistake a 12-year-old for an 8-year-old.

Street children live and work amidst trash, animals and open sewers. Not only are they exposed and susceptible to disease, they are also unlikely to be vaccinated or receive medical treatment.

1. Only two in three Indian children have been vaccinated against
2. TB, Diphtheria, Tetanus, Polio and Measles
3. Only one in ten against Hepatitis B.

Most street children have not been vaccinated at all. They usually can not afford, and do not trust, doctors or medicines. If they receive any treatment at all it will often be harmful, as with kids whose parents place scalding metal on their bellies as a remedy for persistent stomach pain.

Homelessness

Street children in India may be homeless because their family is homeless through poverty or migration, or because they have been abandoned, orphaned or have run away. It is not unusual to see whole families living on the sidewalks of Jaipur, or rows of individual children sleeping around the railway station.

Homeless children have the odds stacked against them. They are exposed to the elements, have an uncertain supply of food, are likely miss out on education and medical treatment, and are at high risk of suffering addiction, abuse and illness. A single child alone on the streets is especially vulnerable.

Poverty

Poverty is the prime cause of the street children crisis. Children from well-off families do not need to work, or beg. They live in houses, eat well, go to school, and are likely to be healthy and emotionally secure.

Poverty dumps a crowd of problems onto a child. Not only do these problems cause suffering, but they also conspire to keep the child poor throughout his/her life. To survive, a poor child in India will probably be forced to sacrifice education and training; without skills the child will, as an adult, remain at the bottom of the economic heap.

Ways in which Help Street Children

- Talk to them in a positive tone, and inquire about their well-being
- If the child looks distressed then report to local Child Welfare Committee or police
- Volunteer at a Centre for street children
- Donate to charity and do fundraising for NGOs
- Campaign for NGOs

Conclusion

Due to the increasing number of urban street children, the incidence of crimes like trafficking and kidnapping increases. It is fuelled by a disruption in schooling and lack of parental care. Presence of Indian and international NGOs is essential in such a scenario, working with local authorities to ensure that these children don't find themselves trapped in substance abuse or victims of abuse and exploitation. Without the knowledge of their rights, they experience torture, harassment and even sexual abuse. You can give a precious few minutes of your time, and work with Save the Children to make a difference. The NGO ranks among an illustrious list of organizations which have shown commitment to making a difference to lakhs of underprivileged children.

References

1. <https://www.savethechildren.in/resource-centre/articles/top-5-ways-in-which-you-can-help-street-children>
2. <https://www.friendsofsbt.org/street-children/>
3. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/UNICEF>
4. <http://childlineindia.org.in/street-children-india.htm>

Web Sources

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8CP-WvW6K-g>
2. <https://www.friendsofsbt.org/street-children/>
3. <http://childlineindia.org.in/street-children-india.htm>
4. http://www.i-indiaonline.com/sc_crisis_theproblem.htm
5. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IBMg6qSzFDQ>
6. <https://steemit.com/life/@koushikbiswas/the-problems-of-street-children>
7. <https://www.savethechildren.in/resource-centre/articles/top-5-ways-in-which-you-can-help-street-children>